

DISTANCE EDUCATION TRAINING SYSTEM: FOREIGN EXPERIENCE

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Abstract: This article examines the achievements and challenges of distance education. It also provides brief solutions and advice on improving the online education system.

Key words: Distance education, digital technology, multimedia capabilities, Moodle.

Introduction: In today's world, the line between online and offline education tends to disappear as more and more people turn to the internet while studying. Nowadays, you can find absolutely any interesting topic on the Internet, this process simplifies the process of finding information and, of course, saves time. The relevance of the topic is that online education has become very popular in recent years and has become an integral part of our lives. This was caused by the emergence of the Covid-19 virus and its unprecedented rapid spread throughout the world. Many changes took place during such a difficult period, which surprised the whole world. One of such radical changes was the intensive transition from the traditional form of education to distance education. This, in turn, led to the direct development of online education and the achievement of great achievements.

Methods of analysis. According to statistics, if students, teachers and all academics and the state support this education system, distance education will develop along with traditional education in the future and become a big results are very likely. A clear example of this is the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. We can mention Mirziyoyev's decision "On additional measures to improve the system of

training, retraining and upgrading of personnel in regional corporate organizations" adopted on September 5, 2018. The fourth paragraph of this decision states the need to give educational institutions the right to organize distance education and all cases are explained in detail. This decree contributed to the development of distance education in the Republic of Uzbekistan as well as in all foreign countries. After all, such support from our head of state has always paid off. In this matter, a lot of work is required from pupils, students, teachers, professors and all persons working in the field of education. To learn more about online language learning, let's take a look back.

Literature analysis. The history of the emergence of online education begins in the 1700s. In 1728, Caleb Phillips placed an advertisement in a Boston newspaper and sought applications by letter exchange for teaching shorthand in every part of the country. In the first half of the 20th century, the development of distance education accelerated in European countries with the emergence of new technologies. In the 1960s, the development of distance education accelerated. In the 1960s, distance education gained international recognition and began to be supported by UNESCO. Every year, the number of online sites is increasing, and at the same time, the quality abroad is improving, and in a short time it began to arrive in the countries of Central Asia. Because, as you can see, distance education itself appeared abroad and is highly developed in these countries. Unique features of online education are modularity. Modularity is one of the unusual features of online education related to the division and fragmentation of a certain system into modules, and the organization of these divisions and the creation of opportunities. Also, the online learning process separates students remotely. That is, during the lesson, students sit quietly, do not disturb or distract each other. Another difference between distance education and traditional education is that it creates an innovative, information society that develops new education. Because a student comes to this environment who clearly understands what skills he needs. That is, in offline education, the ideas that he will come whether he wants to or not will not apply to online education in many cases. Distance learning does not include any in-person interaction with an instructor or study peers. Students study at home on their own, and the learning is more individual and varies on speed and timeline according to each individual student and their availability. Distance learning actually relies on the educational tools of online learning, and that is probably why there is some confusion between the two. It is possible to study with online distance learning as well. In that sense, distance learning is a subset of online learning. Because distance education is remote, it can connect students to universities worldwide, making it more accessible for students in different countries. It is also known to be more affordable, which is another factor that helps make education more

accessible to many students around the world and in different socio-economic levels. If the student wants to read, search, act. In addition, it is one of the most important features to give students and students the opportunity to find the necessary knowledge by themselves using information sources. In addition, according to academics and associate professors, modern teachers have managed to make online education interesting due to various new gadgets, because of the novelty and unusualness of such work for students, they are the most using the latest technologies, they are able to make it interesting and bright in various ways. In addition, distance learning has begun to free teachers from answering students' questions, because thanks to digital technology, they can correct their mistakes, because they can independently analyze and correct mistakes, give feedback. will be, and as a result of this, of course, self-control, upbringing, and self-confidence will begin to develop. Because, in almost all educational organizations: whether it's a school or a university, if a student gives an incorrect answer or the worker is not perfect with his answer, the rest of the students immediately answer for him, which makes the student it leads to a loss of interest and, perhaps, next time the student does not want to answer again, even if he does, he feels uncomfortable. Distance learning avoids these problems.

From the point of view of science and statistics, the development of technologies greatly helps the students of general education schools and higher educational institutions in gaining knowledge, discovering new areas, and learning foreign languages. Because, regardless of distance education or traditional form of education, everything: the results they show directly depend on the efforts of students. That is why modern teachers may not put the form of education in the first place. After all, they know that it is impossible to achieve high results with a weak teaching methodology and inability to interest the student. Therefore, the main goal of a professional pedagogue is to interest the student and give him strong knowledge. online education is not without its downsides, and it is even more so in the corporate world. The main negative aspect of distance learning can be its efficacy. Since this form of training often involves little-to-no hands-on experience, trainees are left with small tangible results. As a result, most people subscribed to online learning tend to fail when they are confronted with challenges in the real world. In addition, staying grounded can prove challenging to participants who would rather learn through conventional means; instances of people quitting online occupational programs are in the majority.

Good readers are active readers. From the outset they have clear goals in mind for their reading. They constantly evaluate whether the text, and their reading of it, is meeting their goals. Good readers typically look over the text before they read, noting such things as the structure of the text and text sections that might be most relevant to

their reading goals. As they read, good readers frequently make predictions about what is to come. They read selectively, continually making decisions about their reading -- what to read carefully, what to read quickly, what not to read, what to re-read, and so on. Good readers construct, revise, and question the meanings they make as they read. They draw upon, compare, and integrate their prior knowledge with material in the text. They think about the authors of the text, their style, beliefs, intentions, historical milieu, and so on. They monitor their understanding of the text, making adjustments in their reading as necessary. Good readers try to determine the meaning of unfamiliar words and concepts in the text, and deal with inconsistencies or gaps as needed.

They evaluate the text's quality and value, and react to the text in a range of ways, both intellectual and emotional. Good readers read different kinds of text differently. For example, when reading narrative, good readers attend closely to the setting and characters; when reading expository text these readers frequently construct and revise summaries of what they have read. For good readers, text processing occurs not only during 'reading' as we have traditionally defined it, but also during short breaks taken during reading, and even after the 'reading' itself has commenced. Comprehension is a consuming and complex activity, but one that, for good readers, is typically both satisfying and productive.

Discussion and conclusion. It is impossible not to emphasize that today's youth, the next generation, who are growing up, have greater conditions, privileges, and time than the previous generations. On the one hand, it should be acknowledged that both modes of learning have numerous benefits. One main desirable aspect of online learning is relatively small expenditure on the part of the learner. Since the learner does not have to commute to another place to take classes, no money is spent on transportation. Similarly, one is generally not required to spend as much on other basic necessities like food and clothing, which can be a great advantage for those who run on a tight budget. As for the potential benefits of learning in the classroom, the most immediate one is social experience, which often constitutes a significant part of one's learning experience. Social interactions that take place in the classroom as well as off-campus with school friends and feedback one receives from their academic surrounding can hardly be substituted by online classes.

Almost all parents try their best to make their child fluent. Students try to find their best way of learning whether online or offline to achieve their goals. Therefore, there is no doubt that if the young generation, without abusing the created conditions, tries to learn with all their energy and intelligence, they will achieve high results and a great career in the country.

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